

ENABLING CROSS-BORDER RESEARCH WITH SENSITIVE DATA VIA IDAN

IDAN INTERNATIONAL
DATA ACCESS NETWORK

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ROADMAP

- **IDAN – INTERNATIONAL DATA ACCESS NETWORK**
- **NEED FOR TRANSNATIONAL DATA ACCESS**
- **IDAN CONCEPT: START WITH QUICK WINS**
- **IDAN – ACHIEVEMENTS SO FAR**
- **NEXT STEPS**

■ IDAN – INTERNATIONAL DATA ACCESS NETWORK

- **Established 2018 (no funding), based on partners' resources and the common goal of collaboration**
 - Partners (2018): 6 RDCs from France (CASD), Germany (IAB-FDZ, GESIS-GML) The Netherlands (CBS), and the United Kingdom (ONS; UKDS SecureLab)
 - Coordinator of IDAN: Roxane Silberman (CASD)
- **General aim**
 - Facilitating cross-national comparative research based on sensitive microdata
 - Improving access to sensitive microdata across national borders for research purposes
- **Focus on data that are**
 - collected at the national level and crucial for public policy evaluation (such as administrative data, official microdata, surveys, and linked data);
 - not already gathered at European level, and are outside the focus of European data producers (e.g. Eurostat, Eurofound, ECB);
 - highly detailed, and often have a very high population coverage;

➤ i.e. sensitive microdata requiring secure access conditions.
- <https://idan.network/>

■ NEED FOR TRANSNATIONAL DATA ACCESS

- **Researcher demand for accessing, pooling and linking administrative microdata**

- A huge amount of administrative data are available at a national level, mostly requiring secure access conditions
- Secure access in place and/or developing in many countries, at national level (e.g. via NSIs; RDCs)
- However, national data silos => not available at European/international level

- **Researcher demand for transnational access**

- Cross-national comparative research, especially in the field of policy evaluation, can generate new insights, if there is the possibility to work with sensitive data from different countries
- Researchers based in different countries need the option to collaborate from their country
- Transnational mobility of researchers: Research stays abroad are part of an academic career => access to sensitive data is needed, regardless of the country of work (compliance with GDPR and statistical laws provided)

- **IDAN's approach: Facilitate research use of secure access data across borders based on reciprocal provision of Safe Room Remote Desktop Access**

■ IDAN CONCEPT: START “WITH QUICK WINS”

- **First insight: the development of an ideal transnational data access system is highly complex, requires too many resources and takes far too much time to implement**
 - Too many issues to solve (legal, contractual, technical, financial ...)
- **Decision for quick wins**
 - Based on the collaboration of a limited number of RDCs
 - Volunteers to move forwards facilitating Safe Room Remote Desktop Access to their sensitive data across borders
 - Based on their own resources (no funding)
- **IDAN concept**
 - Implementation of reciprocal access points in participating RDCs
 - via bilateral contracts (=> no one-size-fits-all-partners contract),
 - via agreements on security requirements for the « IDAN facilities/safe room » hosting the partners access points (=> RDC with the highest security measures has set the standard).
 - Accreditation of researchers, application process, and output control remain in the hands of the RDCs holding the data.
 - A Network website (<https://idan.network/>) provides all necessary information, links to partners' data catalogues, harmonized information on partners' procedures for data access, and links to the procedures.

■ IDAN – OUR AGREEMENTS

Our agreements

Memorandum of Understanding

We work together to promote remote cross-access between countries to secured data. Our collaboration is regulated by a **Collaboration Understanding** (– [view pdf](#)) and bilateral or multilateral contracts.

Partners' procedures

We compare and provide harmonized information on partner's frameworks for secured data, mainly on **accreditation procedures** (– [view pdf](#)). We aim thus to facilitate the use of data from multiple countries.

Agreements

We have agreed on **common security rules** (– [view pdf](#)).

■ IDAN – ACHIEVEMENTS SO FAR: NETWORK OF RDCs

Implementation of access points finalized in 4 RDCs from 3 countries

- **CASD** (Paris - France)
- **IAB/FDZ** Institute for Employment Research/ Federal Employment Agency (Nuremberg - Germany)
- **GESIS** (Mannheim and Cologne - Germany)
- **UKDS** SecureLab (Colchester - United Kingdom)

Implementation of access points was not possible for the 2 other partners, CBS and ONS

- **CBS**: provides remote access across borders but not via a safe room, not in their mandate to host access points
- **ONS**: still busy setting up remote access at a national level

■ IDAN – ACHIEVEMENTS SO FAR: „SOME PEOPLE DO IT RIGHT“

The loss of CBS and ONS is a pity, because as Paolo Paruolo aptly commented with reference to IDAN:

Some people do it right: 1

IDAN international data access network A COLLABORATIVE PROJECT

Collaboration between 6 Research Data Centres from France, Germany, Netherlands and the UK to facilitate research use of controlled access data between these countries.

<https://idan.network/>

We are all sitting on a treasure of administrative data

Source: Paolo Paruolo (2019): Accesso a microdati, ricerca e miglioramento delle politiche: esiste un valore aggiunto europeo? <https://de.slideshare.net/slideshow/p-paruolo-joint-research-centre-the-european-commissions-science-and-knowledge-service-sessione-come-laccesso-ai-microdati-sta-cambiando-il-policy-making/149290737>

■ IDAN ACHIEVEMENTS SO FAR – E.G. USE OF SAFEROOM GESIS MANNHEIM

■ IDAN – ACHIEVEMENTS SO FAR AND FURTHER NEEDS

- **Small Network of RDCs established**
- **Safe Room Remote Desktop Access to sensitive data across borders enabled for researchers**
 - Researchers can use data from various countries/ IDAN member institutions in their ,local‘ RDC
 - Researchers can collaborate with other international researchers using IDAN partners‘ premises
- **Website set up**
- **A framework detailing security and surveillance requirements**
- **A framework to support researchers, where multiple accreditation is needed**

- **Further needs**
 - Evaluation of options for harmonising/sharing Safe Researcher Training where needed
 - Continuous involvement of researchers, their needs and demands, as IDANs driver for future developments

■ IDAN - NEXT STEPS

- **Researcher expectations regarding ideal transnational data access is beyond what IDAN can currently offer**
 - IDAN Expert Online Workshop (2023):
 - Remote Desktop preferred to Saferoom
 - Metadata with more detailed information on data wanted (at least univariate distributions)
 - Pooling of cross-national data should be enabled
 - Language barriers to be overcome
 - Actions:
 - > Feasibility study (IAB/CASD) regarding pooling French & German data; already work in progress
 - > Metadata (for selected data) provided also in English
- **Enlargement of IDAN**
 - Welcome new partners, enlarge the Network
 - Install new access points
 - Flexibility: Allow different options/ different paces -> dynamic path
 - Online Workshop for interested RDCs, Autumn 2025

THANK YOU

<https://idan.network>

CASD

GESIS Leibniz Institute
for the Social Sciences

IAB INSTITUTE FOR EMPLOYMENT
RESEARCH
The Research Institute of the Federal Employment Agency

UK Data Service